

Avoiding the Ambiguity of Quantitative Data Extraction: An Approach to Improve the Quality of Metrics Results

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1. Introduction

In this work, we present our ongoing effort to bring precision to object-oriented metrics definitions. To understand why precision is important, consider the metric Weighted Methods Per Class (WMC), of Chidamber and Kemerer [1], which is expressed as the sum of complexities c of each method M (M_1, \dots, M_n) in a class C . The WMC formal definition is:

$$WMC = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i$$

The idea of complexity in this metric may be interpreted in several ways, according to distinct viewpoints. This implies that two distinct teams collecting the metric results from one system may get different results.

We identified two problems regarding the formality degree used to define metrics: the informal (or natural language) definition problem and mathematical formal definition problem [2, 3]. The former can generate diverge results and the latter requires a strong mathematical background to understand the expressions, which most of software practitioners may not have.

The Object Constraint Language (OCL) [4], a part of the Unified Modeling Language (UML) standard [5], takes an important role to solve these problems. It is used in conjunction with the UML meta-model [6] to allow unambiguous metrics definition, which in turn helps increasing tool support for object-oriented metrics extraction.

In this work, we propose an approach for defining metrics that combines understandability, formality and precision. Our approach is verified and validated for the sake of correction and for guaranteeing the quality of the formalisms.

This process renders possible the comparisons among different sets of metrics, as well as it may be used to establish a common vocabulary among different

stakeholders. As a consequence, the precision of the metrics collection increases, contributing to the overall quality of the Software Engineering process.

2. An Architecture to Avoid Ambiguity

Our solution starts by making use of any UML modeling tool to build models of systems, which are stored in the tool repository. One of these systems is the UML meta-model itself. Typically, a textual file representing each model is generated by a translator (the model can be converted to XML format, for example).

After the file conversion of the model, the meta-model instance generator creates real instances of the entities in the diagram and populates the model (i.e., a plenty of objects, corresponding to the entities in the model, are created). These instances are the base of the assertions that are constructed with OCL. Using the meta-model and its corresponding instances we are formalizing and testing some design sets of metrics that can be found in the literature, extracting metrics from the other models in the repository (examples will be shown in the full version of this paper).

The diagrams that compose the models and their respective objects serve as input to an OCL evaluation tool, which takes the converted representation of the diagram, the added OCL constraints and the instances of the model, and evaluates each of the constraints, showing the results. The OCL evaluator should be capable of verifying whether the constraints are broken or not, for a given workload of user model instances. Moreover, it should evaluate each assertion separately and to provide feedback on which are the design test cases that meet or break the constraints.

We have developed a meta-model instance generator to instantiate the objects corresponding to the meta-classes and also formalized and tested the validity of the MOOD, MOOD2 [7], [8] and MOOSE metrics [1] [9].

Figure 1 – An Architecture to Bring Precision to Metric Results

3. Conclusions and further work

We plan to formalize other well-known design metrics sets. This effort will help to clarify the metrics definitions and to assess their suitability to measure UML designs. Furthermore, the later effort will enable us to propose a quality model for metrics, which will consequently facilitate the creation of meta-metrics – metrics that measure metrics characteristics.

We also plan to make a similar effort based upon the OML (*OPEN Modeling Language*) meta-model. OML emerged from the OPEN (*Object-oriented Process, Environment and Notation*) consortium [10-13].

The precision granted by the formality of OCL comes at a much lower cost, for both practitioners and tool builders, than when using other formal specification constructs. Since UML became a *de facto* standard, both in academia and industry, more and more people are expected to use OCL in their designs and, as such, to understand its syntax and semantics.

We believe that our efforts can indeed contribute to Software Engineering practical aspects, providing better tool support for metrics and also to emphasize the importance of quantitative approaches on industry and academic applications.

4. References

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